

Enabling Innovation through **VERGE**'s Open Data Space based on 5G Network

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Motivation

- ✓ In wireless communications, the general approach of **open data spaces** is to facilitate the unrestricted exchange of data for the benefit of research, development, and also foster the collaboration activities between different stakeholders.
- ✓ **Open data spaces** provide clarification on fundamental components in terms of data accessibility, openness, collaboration, standards, anonymization, privacy, and data quality.
 - ✓ Within the scope of this concept, our primary approach is to preserve the **open data space** of Turkcell's real 5G network that was developed throughout the VERGE project activities.
 - ✓ This will help to foster data-driven innovations and address interoperability concerns to train AI/ML-based models considering the utilization of real 5G network parameters by other stakeholders and researchers.

- ✓ VERGE aims at enhancing the state of the art of edge computing from three innovation vectors:
 - ✓ **“Edge for AI”** defines a flexible, modular and converged Edge platform that is ready to support distributed AI at the edge.
 - ✓ **“AI for Edge”** enables dynamic function placement by managing and orchestrating the underlying physical, network, and compute resources.
 - ✓ **“Security, privacy and trustworthiness for AI”** are addressed to ensure security of the AI-based models against adversarial attacks, privacy of data and models, and transparency in training and execution by providing explanations for model decisions improving trust in models.
- ✓ VERGE will assess the achievements of the three innovation vectors across two use cases: (1) XR-driven edge-enabled industrial B5G applications and (2) edge-assisted autonomous tram operation.

Data Management Plan

- ✓ In terms of data management, our paper outlines design goals, the anticipated dataset for Turkcell's real 5G network, and tactics for exploitation.

A. FAIR Data

- ✓ A transparent data governance structure adheres to the FAIR guiding principles, emphasizing the importance of making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
- ✓ Aligned with the design of the open data space, the FAIR guiding principles uphold the highest standards for accessibility, usability, and integration in data management.

B. Open Data Space Concept

- ✓ VERGE's **open data spaces** enable secure and private platforms for pooling, accessing, processing, and sharing data while safeguarding sensitive information.
- ✓ The pursuit of data quality, availability, and interoperability, as well as a transparent and fair data governance mechanism, are key features.
- ✓ This strategy empowers data creators, encourages collaboration and creativity, and assures project participants and other stakeholders have access to VERGE's **open data space**.

C. Open Data Space Design Objectives

- ✓ The VERGE project's data space design objectives are a strategic framework aiming at creating a diverse and forward-thinking data ecosystem.
- ✓ One of the key goals is to provide **transparency**, **accessibility**, and **collaboration** using open-source solutions.
- ✓ The design also emphasizes **intelligent modularity**, allowing for component replacement and addition as needs evolve. This encourages system **flexibility** and **adaptability**.
- ✓ Furthermore, the design encourages **eco-friendliness**, **scalability**, and **elasticity**, allowing for continuous environmental monitoring and the addition of new users without sacrificing performance.

TURKCELL'S 5G Network Dataset

- ✓ As part of the VERGE project open data space, Turkcell supplies the real 5G network dataset, which is critical for training machine learning (ML) / artificial intelligence (AI) models to monitor and optimize 5G network operations.
- ✓ As shown in Fig. 1, the data is collected from Istanbul Airport and includes a wide range of 5G key performance indicators (KPIs) such as availability, mobility, traffic, and utilization. The glimpse of dataset is provided in Fig. 2 below.

Fig. 1: 5G Indoor network area

DATE TIME	Dist. User Count (Turkcell)	Dist. User Count (Roaming)	User Count (Max)	DL-Data Volume (MB)	UL-Data Volume (MB)	DL Resource Block Util Rate	UL Resource Block Util Rate	User - DL Throughput (Mbps)	Cell - DL Throughput (Mbps)	Cell - UL Throughput (Mbps)	SgNB Addition Success Rate	Intra-SgNB PSCell Change_PC	Inter-SgNB PSCell Change_PC	SgNB-Trigger AbnormSgNB Rel. Ratio
31.12.2023	236	1.880		211.112	27.602			308,60	71,70	26,20				
30.12.2023	370	2.309		233.110	25.687			304,80	69,00	24,70				
29.12.2023	478	2.368	2.276	276.975	24.946	2,37	3,93	361,50	73,50	23,60	99,79	99,90	63,54	0,73
28.12.2023	386	2.097	2.071	239.510	27.987	2,30	3,99	399,10	66,00	24,80	99,95	99,95	54,53	0,63
27.12.2023	356	2.072	1.955	195.974	23.400	2,16	3,82	229,80	63,40	24,20	99,64	99,90	61,79	0,70
26.12.2023	327	2.051	1.878	232.443	17.512	2,25	3,67	321,50	78,40	22,30	99,94	100,00	56,26	0,71
25.12.2023	391	1.675	1.697	164.036	20.652	2,04	3,72	319,10	65,50	24,70	99,95	99,94	53,80	0,67

Fig. 2: The glimpse of collected real 5G network dataset

Benefit and Impact

- ✓ 5G networks adjust numerous industries with their numerous benefits and deep implications.
- ✓ This ecosystem's shared datasets stimulate technical improvements and support data-driven innovations.
- ✓ Dataset shown in Table 1 reveals out the data arranged in such a way that the hourly aggregation of data on a monthly basis is possible while using four 5G radios (gNBs) in a 5G non-stand-alone (NSA) architecture using the 3.5GHz

TABLE I
TURKCELL'S 5G NETWORK DATASET

		Explanation		
Short description	5G network performance data encompassing monitoring metrics in Istanbul Airport for various time periods will be available to train any AI/ML models for 5G network monitoring and optimization.			
Data metrics and KPIs	KPIs obtained include availability, mobility, traffic, and utilization (more specifically, user count, downlink (DL)/uplink (UL) data volume, DL/UL resource block utilization rate, user/cell throughput, secondary gNB cell change rate, and addition success rate).	Findability	Open to all VERGE project partners who are developing AI/ML models.	
Geographic scope	The 5G network data is collected from Istanbul Airport, while numerous users can connect to the gNBs at the same time, and 35% of the airport's allotted space for user mobility is covered. Furthermore, 4 separate gNBs with 5G NSA modes are enabled, with 8 active sectors and 3.5 GHz frequency bandwidth provided for communication.	Accessibility	The dataset will be shared upon request to the approval of the data holder (Turkcell). When necessary, the data owner can provide access to the data to VERGE's project partners involved in project management. This dataset can only be viewed with a specified login and password.	
Frequency of data gathering	On a monthly basis, aggregated data can be delivered every hour.	Re-usability	Available for re-use exclusively for the total period of the project.	
Data collection environment capabilities	Indoors, with varying numbers of users linked to various gNBs.	Data security	Turkcell's dataset can compromise any personal information concerning the confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, and nonrepudiation of information. Therefore, Turkcell can apply technical and organizational security procedures such as various data manipulation techniques to secure and safeguard the stored personal data from unintentional or malicious modification, loss, or destruction.	
Data utilization category	Mostly for the purpose of mobility.	Legal compliances	Collected 5G network data may contain personal information and must be anonymized and masked to safeguard users' privacy. Turkcell 5G network dataset can be shared with VERGE's non-disclosure agreement partner. It is not applicable for external third-party use without the permission of the data holder.	
Focus of 5G key enablers	mMTC and URLLC			
Data augmentation /synthetization	Assuming there is proper user traffic, data is captured from a real 5G network. In this regard, if any of the data cannot be correctly acquired, the dataset is subject to any data augmentation technique or extension to synthetic data.			

Conclusion

- ✓ Specifically, the comprehensive classification of Turkcell's dataset, the formation of a plan for data sharing, the assessment of the geographical scope of the environment in which data is gathered, dedication to the principles of FAIR data, and the careful consideration of legal and ethical norms have all been addressed.
- ✓ In addition, it is emphasized that this dataset will be utilized by collaborators in order to enhance engagement initiatives in both the academic and industrial sectors, as well as to meet the objectives of the project.

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Thank you for your attention!